

extract was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The acidic fraction afforded no crystalline solid. The neutral fraction on chromatographic separation over silica-gel followed by crystallisation furnished two white crystalline solids, m.p. 285-287° and 265-267° respectively. These were identified as taraxeryl acetate⁵ and taraxerol⁶, (m.m.p., T.L.C. and I.R.) with authentic specimens of taraxeryl acetate and taraxerol respectively.

The benzene extract on chromatographic separation over silica-gel also furnished taraxeryl acetate⁵, m.p. 290-95°, identical (m.m.p. and T.L.C.) with an authentic specimen of taraxeryl acetate and taraxerol⁶, m.p. 270-76°, identical (m.m.p. and T.L.C.) with an authentic sample of taraxerol.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly indebted to the University of Kalyani and to Messrs East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., Calcutta for awarding Junior Fellowships to two of them (M. D. and P. K. respectively).

References

1. JOHN M. KINGSBURY, *Poisonous Plants of the United States and Canada*, Hrentice-Hall, New Jersey, 1964, p. 271.
2. GUENTER LEGLER, *Phytochemistry*, 1965, 4, 29.
3. E. JOSEPHY and E. RADT, 'Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry', Springer Verlag, Vol. 14, New York, 1965, p. 90.
4. 'The Wealth of India Raw Materials', Vol. IV, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 127.
5. 'Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry', Vol. 14-S, (Ed.) F. Radt, Elsevier, 1952, p. 1191 S.
6. 'Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry', Vol. 14-S, (Ed.) F. Radt, Elsevier, 1952, p. 1190 S.

Chemical Examination of the Roots of *Gardenia turgida* Roxb

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Manuscript received 7 August 1978,

revised 16 November 1978, accepted 22 December 1978

GARDENIA *turgida* Roxb (Rubiaceae) is a small spiny tree occurring throughout the greater part of India. Some parts of this plant have already been examined by different workers^{1,2}. The present communication embodies the chemical study on its roots and D-mannitol, gardenin A, gardenin B, gardenin E, oleanolic acid, α -amyrin and β -sitosterol have been isolated from the ethanolic extract.

The ethanol extract of the air dried roots was concentrated to 200 ml and kept in refrigerator, when a good amount of amorphous resinous matter

separated out. This was removed by decantation (Ethanol-insoluble fraction) and the mother liquor, fractionated into acidic and neutral sapogenins³. The neutral fraction was obtained in too small quantity to permit its isolation and identification.

Examination of Ethanol-insoluble Fraction :

The ethanol-insoluble portion was washed with hot benzene to remove waxy impurities and the resultant brown-yellow resinous mass was chromatographed over a column of deactivated alumina. Pure methanol furnished D-mannitol, m.p. 164-65°; hexacetyl, m.p. 120°; hexabenzooate, m.p. 147-48°; identical with authentic specimen.

Examination of Acidic Sapogenin Mixture :

The thick resinous acidic fraction on chromatography over silica gel gave following compounds :

Gardenin A—Light petroleum-benzene (1 : 1) yielded yellow needles, m.p. 163-64° (lit^{4,5} m.p. 164-65°); positive Wilson boric acid, Dimroth, Asahina and Inubuse and Shinoda tests; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm^{-1} 3350 (-OH stretch), 1660 (C=O stretch); PMR (CDCl_3); consistent with one reported by Seshadri *et al*⁴; acetate, m.p. 134-35° and methyl ether, m.p. 115°.

Gardenin B—Light petroleum-benzene (1 : 3) afforded fine needles, m.p. 177-78° (EtOH); M^+ 358. IR and NMR spectra were in concordance with those of an authentic sample⁶.

Gardenin E—Pure benzene eluted a compound as yellow needles, m.p. 230-31°; positive colour tests for 5-hydroxy flavones. Its identity was established by comparison with an authentic sample as well as by Co-IR, PMR and mass spectra.

Oleanolic acid—Benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) afforded colourless needles, m.p. 305-6° (MeOH); ν_{\max} (Nujol) cm^{-1} 3200 (-OH stretch), 1710, 1680 (-CO stretch); acetate, m.p. 266-67° and methyl ester, m.p. 193-94°.

α -**Amyrin**—Benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) fraction was crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 183-84°. The identity was proved by Co-IR, Co-TLC, m.m.p. as well as by preparation of acetate, m.p. 222-23° and benzoate, m.p. 193°.

β -**Sitosterol**—The colourless flakes, m.p. 136-37° (MeOH) obtained from benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 3) were directly compared with an authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Dr. M. Krishnamurti of Delhi University for supplying authentic samples of gardenin A and E. One of us (R.T.P.) also thanks the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of J.R.F.

References

1. The Wealth of India, Raw Materials, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, Vol. IV, 1956, 108.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, 123.
3. L. RAMCHANDRA RAO, M. GOPALA RAO and C. RUKMINI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 1203.
4. T. R. SHESHADRI and K. J. BALAKRISHNA, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 91, 260.
5. K. VENKATARAMAN and A. V. RAMARAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 677.
6. K. VENKATARAMAN, A. V. RAMARAO, P. CHAKRABARTI, A. K. SANYAL and P. K. BOSE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 398.

Iodine Promoted Thermal Cyclisation of Anthranilic Acid

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Manuscript received 19 April 1978, accepted 3 November 1978

DIPHENYLAMINE(I) and aniline(II) were shown to cyclise to carbazole(III) under iodine promoted thermal cyclisation^{1,2}. Aniline was, however shown to give host of other products including diphenylamine. Recently Bradenberger *et al*³ have shown that aniline cyclises to diphenylamine and carbazole. In consideration of our interest in the Rutaceae alkaloids^{4,5} of anthranilate origin⁶, we were interested to investigate the fate of anthranilic acid(IV) under this oxidative cyclisation reaction. In the present communication, we report the formation of diphenylamine(I), carbazole(III), acridone(V) and *o*-aminobenzophenone(VI) as significant products by iodine promoted thermal cyclisation of (IV).

Anthranilic acid was heated in a sealed tube containing oxygen and trace of iodine at 350° for 3 hours. The reaction products were taken up in benzene, fractionated into basic and neutral fractions and then chromatographed over alumina. From the neutral fractions diphenylamine(I) mp 56° ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 240, 286 nm with log ϵ 3.90, 4.22), carbazole(III) mp 230° ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 233, 257, 293 nm with log ϵ 4.5, 4.18, 4.10) were isolated. These form the major products of reactions. From the basic fraction acridone, mp 354° ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 251, 254, 295, 308, 370, 381, 400 nm with log ϵ 4.76, 4.78, 3.33, 3.05, 3.63, 3.93, 3.95) and *o*-aminobenzophenone mp 103° ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 234 nm with log ϵ 4.37) were isolated.

All these compounds were identified by comparison with authentic specimens by t.l.c., mmp., and uv spectra. The formation of (I) and (III) from (II) is well documented^{2,3}. They could arise here from (IV) by ready decarboxylation of (IV) to (II) and subsequent cyclisation. The formation of *o*-aminobenzophenone could be conceived to arise by the acylation of benzene fragment. The formation of aminobenzophenone by deamination of aniline through a benzyne intermediate⁷ cannot be ruled out.

The formation of the skeletal units (V, VI) of some of the alkaloids of Rutaceae by oxidative cyclisation of anthranilic acid and related compounds, the biogenetic hypothesis of the formation of acridone alkaloid from VI by Bowen *et al*⁸ and the recent report of Tecleanone (IX) in *Teclea grandifolia* open out the question of the formation of these alkaloids alternatively by oxidative cyclisation of anthranilic acid or its derivative under the biochemical interactions of appropriate oxidative enzymes.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their respectful thanks to Dr. S. C. Bhattacharyya, Director and Prof. A. Sen, Head of the Dept. of Chemistry for their interest in the work.

References

1. A. ISLAM, P. BHATTACHARYYA and D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Chem. comm.* 1972, 537.
2. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, A. ISLAM and (Miss) M. SARKAR, *Proc. 5th International Symp. on the Chemistry of Natural Products*, held at Ljubljana, Yugoslavia, 1975, 341.